

Supplemental Table S4

Summary of color codes presented in illustrations.

		Magenta/Red	Green	Blue/cyan	White	Gray
Figure 1	panel A, C (stereomicroscopic image)					
	panel B, D, E, G (fluorescence image)	glucagon	CK7	insulin	nuclei	transmitted light
	panel F, H (H&E image)					
Figure 2	panel A-C (stereomicroscopic image)					
	panel D-G (H&E image)					
Figure 3	panel A, F, O (stereomicroscopic image)					
	panel B, C, G-J (H&E image)					
	panel D, E, K-N, P (fluorescence image)	glucagon	CK7	insulin	nuclei	transmitted light
Figure 4	panel A-D, G, N, O (stereomicroscopic image)					
	panel B'-D' (IHC image, CgA)					
	panel H-J (fluorescence image)			PGP9.5	nuclei	
	panel K, L (IHC image, Ki-67)					
	panel P, Q (fluorescence image)	glucagon	CK7	insulin	nuclei	transmitted light
	panel R (H&E image)					
Figure 5	panel B, E, H (fluorescence image)	glucagon	CK7	insulin	nuclei	transmitted light
	panel C-D, F-G, I-J (H&E image)					
Suppl. Fig. 1	panel A, G (stereomicroscopic image)					
	panel B, D, F, H, J, L (fluorescence image)	glucagon	CK7	insulin	nuclei	transmitted light
	panel C, E, I, K (H&E image)					
Suppl. Fig. 2	panel A ₁ -A ₂ (stereomicroscopic image)					
	panel A ₃ -A ₅ (H&E image)					
Suppl. Fig. 3	panel A-C (stereomicroscopic image)					
	panel D (fluorescence image)	glucagon	CK7	insulin	nuclei	transmitted light
	panel E (fluorescence image)	CD31		PGP9.5	nuclei	
	panel F, H (IHC image, CgA)					
	panel G, I (H&E image)					
	panel J, K (IHC image, CD45)					
	panel L, M (IHC image, Ki-67)					
	panel N-P (stereomicroscopic image)					
	panel Q, R (H&E image)					
Suppl. Fig. 4	panel A, B, D (fluorescence image)	CD31	D2-40		nuclei	transmitted light
	panel C (transmitted light image)					transmitted light
Suppl. Video 1	Fluorescence & transmitted light signals	glucagon	CK7	insulin	nuclei	transmitted light

IHC image: image acquired from standard immunohistochemistry. CgA: chromogranin A.

CK7 (epithelial marker); chromogranin A (neuroendocrine lesion marker); PGP9.5 (neuroendocrine marker for nerve, islet, and microadenoma labeling); CD31 (endothelial marker for blood vessel labeling); D2-40 (lymphatic endothelial marker for lymphatic vessel labeling); CD45 (leukocyte common antigen); Ki-67 (proliferation marker).